

Original Research

Explaining the Development Pattern of Management Accounting Services Market

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Abstract

Given the importance and role of customers in maintaining and enhancing the market share of reporting entities to ensure their continued presence in the market, and considering the availability of necessary data for decision-making, the application of management accounting techniques is of significant importance. Addressing the existing gap in the market for such services in Iran, the present study aims to develop a framework for expanding the market for management accounting services in the country. This study is qualitative in nature, with data collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews conducted with financial managers of industrial units in 2024. The process continued until theoretical saturation was achieved. Respondents were selected using the snowball sampling method. Data analysis was carried out based on the Grounded-Theory approach. Based on the study's findings, focusing on creating a need for cost accounting systems, corporate governance, and oversight as causal factors can lead to the development of the market for management accounting services in Iran. Based on research findings, by focusing on creating the need for a costing system, corporate governance, and supervision, it is possible to help develop the market for management accounting services. The results of this study can not only enrich the research literature but also contribute to the development of the market for management accounting services. This, in turn, can create the necessary conditions for improving the quality of products or services and increasing the profitability of reporting entities.

Keywords: Accounting, Accounting Development, Dynamic Theory, Management Accounting, Management Accountants.

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Introduction

According to Adam Smith's theory of division of labor, accounting has been subdivided into various specialized fields, one of which is Managerial Accounting (MA). This claim aligns with several concepts, including Strategic MA, which emphasizes the efficient use of accurate information for strategic decision-making; Transaction Cost Economics, which focuses on the impact of transaction-related costs and their effect on the structure of reporting entities; and Contingency Theory, which addresses the design of accounting systems and decision-making processes within organizations. The primary role of MA is to provide the necessary information for managers to establish a framework for decision-making. In this regard, Conceptual Statement No. 1 of the FASB highlights that the most important function of an accounting information system is to provide useful information for decision-making (Mellemvik, Monsen, & Olson, 1988: 101). Decision-making requires acquiring relevant information on the subject at hand (Citroen, 2011: 493), a task that has been significantly facilitated by advancements in IT.

In today's dynamic environment, characterized by changes in the business landscape, the critical role of customers, the concept of competition, technological advancements, globalization, and other similar factors (Hansen, Mowen, & Guan, 2009: v), access to timely and accurate information is considered a competitive advantage for Reporting Entities (RE). Moreover, the role of information in decision-making outcomes cannot be overstated. Managers, in their efforts to ensure the survival of RE, are compelled to maintain and enhance quality while simultaneously increasing profit margins by reducing the cost of goods and services. Achieving this necessitates strategic decision-making, which, in turn, depends on accurate and detailed information provided by MA departments.

Research findings indicate that MA techniques are employed to improve the performance of RE. Additionally, some studies have highlighted the use of MA systems in enhancing supply chain performance in manufacturing entities (Almatarneh, Jarah, & Jarrah, 2022) and product development (Varaniūtė, Žičkutė, & Žandaravičiūtė, 2022). These findings underscore the global reliance on MA services. However, unlike the international goods and services market, the utilization of MA services has not gained adequate attention among managers in Iran. This raises important questions: What factors lead to the lack of demand for MA services? Why are these services not used to improve goods and services? Why is MA less prioritized compared to financial accounting? What factors contribute to the gap in the application of MA services between domestic and international markets?

Given the importance of MA in maintaining and sustaining businesses, this study aims to address these questions. To achieve its objectives, the present research employs a qualitative approach based on GT. GT facilitates identifying the underlying factors contributing to this lag from a positivist theoretical perspective. Understanding the issue can pave the way for its resolution and help overcome the current situation.

The findings of this study reveal that factors such as the perceived need for cost accounting systems, corporate governance, and oversight can positively influence the adoption of MA services. These outcomes could lead to improved quality and reduced

costs of goods and services, ensuring the survival of RE while preserving and expanding their market share. Following the theoretical framework, the research will proceed by detailing the methodology, data collection process, and analysis, setting the stage for discussion and conclusions.

Material & Methods

MA, as a specialized field of accounting, serves the critical function of meeting managers' informational needs for decision-making. In other words, MA can be regarded as a catalyst for organizational change and progress (Mirbagheri Roodbari & Kordestani, 2020). Its historical evolution can be divided into two phases: the pre-1950 era, encompassing the periods of the Industrial Revolution, mass production, and World War II; and the post-industrial era (post-1950), characterized by strategic planning, competitive schools of thought, and other emerging frameworks (Vatan Parast, Tasaddi Kari, & AhmadZadeh Layegh, 2018: 49).

Accounting is deeply rooted in its environment and, given the constant changes in the external environment, user needs also evolve accordingly. As a result, accounting systems must adapt to these shifting requirements. This necessity led to the development of Modern Costing Systems (MCS) following the identification of inefficiencies and environmental misalignment in traditional costing methods (Kamal, 2015: 13). Traditional systems were inadequate in addressing audience demands due to factors such as increased competition, technological advancements, globalization, the significance of time as a competitive element, and similar influences (Hansen, Mowen, & Guan, 2009: v). Research by Bork and Morgan (1993) on RE using traditional costing systems demonstrated their inability to meet user informational needs (Kamal, 2015: 13). Consequently, modern costing techniques, many of which emerged in the 1990s, were introduced to address these deficiencies (Vatan Parast, Tasaddi Kari, & AhmadZadeh Layegh, 2018: 49).

Given that costs are the primary controllable tool for managers in maintaining profitability and ensuring the survival of RE, the strategic importance of MA in rational decision-making is undeniable. For instance, research by Elshaer (2022) shows that employing second-generation costing (time-driven activity-based costing) serves as a suitable basis for cost determination in restaurants (Elshaer, 2022: 1). These findings implicitly affirm the accuracy, flexibility, and applicability of modern costing approaches across various sectors. Similarly, Campos et al. (2022) highlight that using modern MA techniques with a long-term perspective can ensure the sustainability of hotels in their businesses. They argue that the most critical tool for guaranteeing revenue in this industry is the use of budgeting techniques (Campos et al., 2022: 257).

A study by Vu, Dam, and Ha (2022) on the factors influencing MA adoption in Vietnamese logistics RE identified five key determinants: organizational size, structure, technological advancement, implementation costs, and strategies (Vu, Dam, & Ha, 2022: 27). Their findings confirm the significant role of MA techniques in fostering effective and efficient decision-making. They also assert that these techniques contribute to value creation and enhanced performance from both financial and non-financial perspectives. However, Campos et al. argue that despite their benefits, implementing these techniques

faces challenges, with managers often hesitant to adopt them in short-term horizons (Campos et al., 2022: 257). Gunarathne, Lee, and Hitigala Kaluarachchilage (2021) emphasize the environmental role of MA and its importance in enhancing sustainability through accountability mechanisms. Their research highlights that environmental accountability is a crucial factor in developing MA systems (Gunarathne, Lee & Hitigala Kaluarachchilage 2021: 825). Ahmad and Mohamed Zabri (2015) found that the size of REs, the intensity of competition, the need to maintain market share, managerial commitment, and the level of IT development significantly influence the adoption of MA services (Ahmad & Mohamed Zabri, 2015: 762). Wanderley and Cullen (2013) categorize the drivers for MA adoption into external and internal factors. External factors include market pressure, government regulations, customer expectations, technological advancements, and environmental changes. Internal factors involve organizational dynamics, size, complexity, and approaches to problem-solving (Wanderley & Cullen, 2013: 303). In Iran, research by Bolouri, Mahmoudzadeh Baghbani, and Rezaei (2019) reveals that cultural, organizational, legal, and educational shortcomings hinder the application of MA systems in the healthcare sector (Bolouri, Mahmoudzadeh Baghbani & Rezaei, 2019: 49). Similarly, Bahramfar, Khajavi, and Nazemi (2008) identified four primary barriers to adopting MA techniques in companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange: managers' unfamiliarity with MA concepts and methods, insufficient academic training, delays in timely accounting information, and frequent economic policy changes (Bahramfar, Khajavi & Nazemi, 2008: 93).

Research Methodology

This study can be categorized from various perspectives. In terms of its approach, it is a qualitative and positivist research. The data is gathered with the aim of understanding "what exists" rather than "what ought to be," based on insights derived directly from the societal context (Tasaddi Kari et al., 2023: 61). This approach allows the researcher to identify and better comprehend the environmental context in which actions and phenomena occur (ibid.: 62). Therefore, the research is exploratory in nature.

In this research, the GT method was employed, a qualitative approach first introduced by Glaser and Strauss in 1965. GT aims to understand what occurs within the contextual environment. The study's statistical population includes 10 FM from manufacturing RE. These participants were selected through the snowball sampling method. As noted earlier, these managers work in manufacturing-industrial units and have over 10 years of professional experience. The process of data collection and exploration of various dimensions of the research topic was conducted using existing books and articles, the constant comparative technique, and assumptions extracted from reflective notes and field observations. This iterative process continued until theoretical saturation was reached for each category. Data analysis and initial coding of each interview were performed using MAXQDA-10 software, and the findings from one interview were analyzed before conducting the subsequent one.

In this research, following the methodology of Tasaddi Kari et al. (2023), face and content validity methods were utilized to ensure validity. These methods relied on the evaluations of field experts—FM with over 10 years of professional experience. Validity in this context refers to the capability of an instrument to measure the intended

characteristic (ibid.). Therefore, achieving high validity in the design of the resulting research pattern is a primary consideration. To assess the validity of the measurement tools, this study adopted a judgment-based approach using the insights and perspectives of the aforementioned experts, as per the framework established by Tasaddi Kari et al.

Results

To collect data for this study, interviews were conducted with FM from manufacturing industries, each with over 10 years of executive experience in financial management. Using the GT method, data were analyzed after conducting open interviews and reaching theoretical saturation, at which point no new concepts or categories emerged during the final interview. The demographic details of the respondents are presented in Table 1, providing descriptive statistics about the participants.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

Gender	Frequency
Male	7
Female	3
Total	10

This table summarizes the demographic distribution of respondents based on their gender, indicating that the majority of participants were male seven, while female respondents numbered three.

After conducting the interviews and reaching theoretical saturation, with no new concepts or categories emerging during the final interview, the data were analyzed using the GT method and MAXQDA-10 software. In this research, for the coding process, the interviews were transcribed, and after reviewing and re-reading, the necessary concepts were extracted. Given the nature of the GT method and its execution guidelines, each statement from the interviewees was assigned a code. The process of selecting the codes was carried out with the aim of explaining the research topic and with great care, and whenever possible, in consultation with the interviewees. This process aimed to create a cohesive set of initial codes and concepts, which involved a careful examination of the statements from each interview. In this study, the overall concept was identified through line-by-line and phrase-by-phrase content analysis, and the commonalities between the open codes, concepts, and categories were defined based on conceptualization, categorization, and similarity. The details of the categorization are presented in five main areas: causal factors, contextual factors, intervening factors, strategies, and outcomes.

Causal Conditions

These conditions refer to events, occurrences, or incidents that lead to the emergence or development of a phenomenon. A phenomenon refers to the main idea, incident, event, or occurrence that is associated with a set of actions or reactions for its management, or a series of actions related to it. In this study, the set of causal conditions is categorized into three main categories and ten subcategories, which are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Open Codes and Concepts of Causal Conditions

Main Category	Subcategory	Concepts
Need for a Costing System	Cost Reduction	Accurate costing; precision in reported costs; specialized cost presentation; and cost monitoring.
	Real Costing	Focus on profit; performance monitoring; performance management; and accurate reporting.
	Cost Management (CM)	Prevention of price manipulation; realistic pricing; and efficient pricing.
	Use of Updated Costing Systems	Coordination and consistency; limitations of traditional (industrial) costing; and providing more details, speed, and accuracy in reporting.
Corporate Governance	Accurate Cost Reporting	Precision in costing and appropriate analysis; accuracy in MA; and attention to detail in work.
	Stakeholders' Benefits	Transparency in cost reporting; access to accurate information; and faster access to management reports.
	Agency Costs	Alignment of agent and principal interests; elimination of information asymmetry; and transparent costing information.
Supervision	Market and Competitor Monitoring	Transparency of reporting units; competitive strategies; precision in development; and accurate competitive costs.
	Awareness of Regulatory Bodies	Obligation for real costing; awareness of profit and costs; transparency and accuracy; and institutional awareness of operational processes.
	Reliability of Reports	Management reports; costing and pricing reports; and awareness of the reporting unit's operational processes.

Causal Conditions

Need for a Costing System

Respondents believe that the development of MA is linked to the perceived need to manage costs and prevent unnecessary expenses. Specifically, when costs arise, it is essential not only to focus on the effectiveness of the expense but also on its economic feasibility.

When RUs carefully identify and control their costs and utilize MCS, this leads to resource optimization and minimizes unnecessary expenditures. This results in increased profit margins and improved economic performance of RUs. On the other hand, from the respondents' perspective, accuracy in costing is also crucial. By accurately monitoring performance and ensuring correct reporting, RUs can obtain more accurate information about costs and revenues. This precision allows for more effective costing because RUs can make better strategic decisions based on accurate data. As decision-making relies on having relevant information about the matter at hand (Azadi & Mirzaei, 2013: 11). Moreover, CM, through cost transparency and precise control, prevents incorrect costing and leads to the actualization of prices. The outcome of this is the accurate determination of prices based on the real performance of RUs, which leads to optimal CM. Given that traditional costing systems cannot process complex data and analysis with high accuracy and transparency, the need for MCS is expected to intensify.

Corporate Governance (CG)

Respondents emphasize concepts related to the accuracy of cost reporting within CG. CG, through the establishment of supervisory structures, transparent policies, and managerial accountability, contributes to improving the accuracy of cost reporting. Strengthening the supervision of the board of directors and financial committees reduces the likelihood of deviations or distortions in financial information. Moreover, CG, by enhancing transparency and adhering to accounting principles, improves internal controls and prevents opportunistic behaviors. Thus, sufficient accuracy in costing and cost analysis enhances financial transparency and management efficiency. This transparency leads to more accurate reports, and as a result, stakeholders receive the necessary information for decision-making with greater confidence. Therefore, with access to accurate and transparent information, stakeholders can make better decisions that align with their interests. On the other hand, respondents believe that reducing information asymmetry between managers and stakeholders plays a crucial role in improving relationships and reducing conflicts of interest. When information is provided accurately and promptly to stakeholders, agency costs are reduced. Consequently, reducing agency costs, as a subcategory, plays a key role in decreasing conflicts and improving financial and managerial efficiency.

Supervision

From the respondents' perspective, when a reporting unit can provide accurate and transparent information about its performance and competitive costs, it effectively strengthens market and competitor supervision. This is because transparent information not only increases the trust of investors and other stakeholders but also allows for better comparison with competitors and more precise market condition analysis. As a result, this transparency enhances competitive positioning and leads to more informed strategic decision-making. In other words, transparency in this regard enables the reporting unit to operate correctly in the competitive market and helps supervisory bodies access more complete information. This, in turn, improves market and competitor supervision through informational transparency. Additionally, the awareness of supervisory bodies regarding the economic and financial status of RUs is highly significant. When supervisory bodies have access to accurate information about the financial performance of RUs, they can

exercise more effective oversight of their financial and operational processes. This awareness, which results from access to clear and accurate information, leads to improved overall market performance and prevents mistakes and violations. Respondents believe that supervisory bodies, by setting standards and frameworks for financial reporting, contribute to creating transparency, accuracy, and integrity in financial reports. These bodies enforce requirements and controls to ensure that RUs provide reliable financial information that aligns with MA principles. Furthermore, supervisory bodies, by actively overseeing the performance of RUs, prevent potential deviations in financial reporting and facilitate the improvement of MA processes. Thus, the presence of supervisory bodies, by reducing information asymmetry and increasing public trust, contributes to the sustainable development of MA markets. Ultimately, the reliability of reports is also considered an important factor in improving supervision from the respondents' point of view. When managerial and costing reports are accurate and transparent, supervisory bodies can trust them and base their strategic decision-making on this information. The reliability of reports allows supervisory bodies to correctly assess the performance of RUs and monitor the transparency and accuracy of financial operations. All these factors—market and competitor supervision, awareness of supervisory bodies, and the reliability of reports—lead to the subcategory of efficient supervision. This subcategory, in turn, plays a key role in achieving comprehensive oversight, which ultimately improves overall market performance and increases transparency and trust in RUs.

Contextual Conditions (CCs)

CCs refer to the setting or environment where events or incidents related to the phenomenon occur along a certain dimension, within which interactions take place to control, manage, and respond to the phenomenon (Strauss & Corbin, 2014). The category of CCs is presented with one main category and three subcategories in Table 3.

Table 3. Open Codes and Categories of CCs

Main Category	Subcategory	Concepts
Creating Infrastructure	Training	Education on fundamentals and concepts; professional principles; alignment with standards; specialized university training; and developing a specialized field MA.
	Developing Skilled Workforce	Combined academic and practical training; work aligned with standards; and training current professionals on contemporary topics.
	Government and Investor Support	Collaboration between the government and professionals; establishment of more professional institutions and associations; economic stability; and elimination of existing barriers.

According to the respondents, economic factors are among the key concepts in CCs. A stable economic environment helps RE gain a better understanding of their financial status. When markets suffer from significant economic volatility and uncertainty, it becomes challenging for these entities to effectively plan and forecast their costs and revenues. Such economic conditions, especially in the context of competition, heighten

the need for thorough market and economic analyses. Moreover, regulations and laws play a critical role in this regard. If existing laws and regulations require RE to adhere to specific standards, it contributes to greater transparency and trust in the market. This, in turn, fosters a competitive environment, which can ultimately support the development of the MA services market. In addition, respondents believe that human and technological capabilities can also drive the growth of the MA market. RE should leverage skilled and well-trained personnel to analyze and control costs effectively. Access to advanced technologies and MCS enables these entities to analyze more accurate data and make better decisions. On the other hand, respondents emphasized the importance of organizational culture and the acceptance of innovation as significant contextual factors. Organizations that promote a culture of innovation and learning are better positioned to capitalize on environmental and market changes. Such an organizational culture allows RE to quickly respond to evolving market needs and seize new opportunities.

Intervening Conditions

Intervening conditions refer to overarching factors that influence the processes and strategies, either intensifying or weakening phenomena (Strauss & Corbin, 2014). These conditions are presented in Table 4 with one main category and three subcategories.

Table 4. Open Codes and Categories of Intervening Conditions

Main Category	Subcategory	Concepts
Environmental Conditions	Environmental Changes	Fluctuations in exchange rates and costs; economic volatility; inflation; and active industries.
	Law	Lack of stability; insufficient oversight; and professional requirements not being enforceable by law.
	Geographic Environment	Lack of industry; demand in the targeted geography; and advancements in technology and innovation.

According to the respondents, environmental changes are one of the key factors in the development of the MA services market. Economic fluctuations, changes in exchange rates, and inflation, as components of environmental changes, have profound impacts on how RE manage their costs and profits. When economic volatility is severe or unpredictable, decision-making becomes challenging for managers. This situation increases the risks associated with strategic and financial decisions, as RE are unable to plan effectively due to economic instability. Under such conditions, the need for more precise tools and techniques for costing and CM becomes critical. These tools enable RE to optimize resources and reduce costs with greater accuracy. Respondents also highlighted the role of regulations as another significant intervening factor. A lack of stability and insufficient oversight of accounting and financial reporting processes can play a major role in either weakening or strengthening the adoption of MA systems. When accounting-related laws and regulations are not clear, comprehensive, or adequately enforced, RE face challenges in properly implementing accounting processes. Furthermore, the absence of precise and enforceable professional standards can

undermine transparency and trust in the accounting system. In such situations, the formulation and implementation of stronger, more comprehensive regulations are essential to enhance the performance of MA, as well as to improve transparency and efficiency in the market.

On the other hand, respondents identified the geographical environment as another intervening factor that plays a key role in the development of the MA services market by influencing demand and technological advancement. In regions where industries are underdeveloped or markets operate monopolistically, RE may use advanced MA techniques less frequently or opt not to adopt them at all. This is often due to a lack of competitive necessity, insufficient financial and technological infrastructure, as well as cultural and organizational constraints. In such areas, the absence of access to skilled professionals and modern technologies leads these entities to rely on traditional accounting methods. Consequently, in regions where technological advancement is slow, the adoption of MCS and advanced accounting tools is less common. Therefore, to support the growth of the MA services market, greater attention must be given to fostering technological advancement and developing appropriate infrastructure. By doing so, RE can be encouraged to adopt innovative accounting techniques and move away from outdated practices.

Strategies and Outcomes

Strategies refer to proposed solutions for addressing a phenomenon, aimed at managing the phenomenon under study or determining the degree of sensitivity in dealing with it (Strauss & Corbin, 2014). The strategies and outcomes are presented in Table 5, categorized into two main categories and five subcategories.

Table 5. Open Codes and Categories of Strategies and Outcomes

Main Category	Subcategory	Concepts
Strategies	Developing Effective Strategies	Establishing frameworks; documented requirements; framework-based programs; problem-solving; task descriptions; resource management.
	Strategic Planning	Strategic planning; effective planning; foresight; forward-looking reports; goal-setting; strategy formulation.
	Efficiency	Efficient planning; productivity; optimal costing; flexibility; accuracy; desirability.
Outcomes	Desirable and High-Quality Development of the MA Services Market	Effective costing and pricing; increased transparency and reliability; enhanced information systems; reduced agency costs.
	Advancing the MA Profession	Increased trust in the profession; legal and professional mandates to use professional services; development of MA reporting; enhanced credibility of the profession.

Strategies, as systematic and goal-oriented programs, play a crucial role in addressing the challenges present in the MA services market. According to the respondents, key strategies include developing effective approaches, establishing structured frameworks, and improving efficiency. Developing effective strategies requires identifying the needs and priorities of the market, particularly in competitive conditions. These strategies should account for environmental changes and emerging trends, focusing on resource optimization and productivity enhancement. Establishing structured frameworks is essential for guiding processes and defining responsibilities. This approach enhances clarity in roles, improves communication, and standardizes processes. As a result, it contributes to increased efficiency, improved service quality, and more informed managerial decision-making. Additionally, structured frameworks serve as benchmarks for evaluating performance and achieving strategic objectives, further reinforcing their significance in driving the success of MA initiatives.

According to the respondents, improving efficiency is another key aspect of strategies, achieved through the adoption of modern accounting techniques and advanced technologies. This can lead to reduced operational costs and increased profitability for RE. Outcomes, as the final results of strategy implementation, especially in MA, hold significant importance. One of the fundamental outcomes is the effective improvement of MA, which is achieved through the successful execution of strategies. This involves enhancing the accuracy of reporting, more effective CM, and improving the quality of financial information, all of which aid in strategic decision-making. Furthermore, enhancing the position of the MA profession, as another outcome, can lead to increased public trust and higher demand for Accounting Services (AS). By improving service quality and implementing legal and professional requirements, not only will the credibility of the MA profession rise, but it will also attract more clients and improve market performance. Ultimately, strategies and outcomes are interlinked: the effective implementation of strategies can lead to positive results in developing the MA services market, and these outcomes, in turn, reinforce and strengthen the strategies.

Axial coding refers to a series of procedures that connect categories and subcategories, linking the data to one another. This coding process involves the formation of categories through the use of a paradigm to demonstrate the relationships between the elements above. A conceptual model derived from the axial codes is presented in the Figure 1.

Based on the paradigmatic model of the research, the total events and occurrences that lead to the emergence and development of the core phenomenon, which is the development of the MA services market, require a costing system, corporate governance, and supervision. Additionally, the contexts that influence the selection of various strategies and can facilitate and accelerate the implementation of these strategies include the main category of creating infrastructure, which encompasses three subcategories: training, developing specialized personnel, and government and investor support. Ultimately, strategies with the main category of developing effective strategies will lead to the desirable and high-quality development of the MA services market.

Figure 1. Paradigmatic Model of the Research

Discussion

The aim of this research is to propose a pattern for the development of the MA services market using the GT method. Accordingly, this study seeks to identify and analyze the factors influencing the performance of MA in Iran and to offer solutions for improving the current state of this market. The results derived from data analysis and interviews reveal that various factors, including environmental changes, regulations, and geographical characteristics, directly affect the development of the MA services market. The analysis highlights that economic fluctuations and exchange rate volatility are the most significant intervening conditions, posing serious challenges for RE. Severe economic instability leads to uncertainty in forecasting revenues and expenses, creating substantial difficulties for FM who must make strategic decisions. For instance, during periods of exchange rate volatility, manufacturing entities face significant challenges in pricing their products and managing costs. Such instability disrupts financial planning and undermines the confidence of clients and stakeholders in MA services. Volatility brings consequences that include its impact on forecasts and budgeting, risk management, investment decisions, and ongoing monitoring and adjustment. Volatility can negatively affect forecasts and budgeting plans, leading to widespread deviations, which in turn increases the risk for reporting entities. Therefore, the negative impact of these issues on shareholders and investors is not unexpected. Additionally, these factors will impose the cost of continuous monitoring and repeated planning on reporting entities in order to mitigate the negative effects of volatility. Moreover, unstable regulations and insufficient oversight have been identified as major barriers to the efficiency and quality of MA services. The lack of comprehensive and clear accounting and financial regulations can result in confusion when implementing accounting practices, thereby reducing the quality of services provided. These circumstances negatively impact the financial outcomes of RE, exposing them to higher risks. The absence of strong regulatory bodies further exacerbates the lack of transparency in financial processes. Geographical environment and local characteristics also have a direct impact on the demand for AS. In regions where industries are underdeveloped or where the demand for AS is low, RE are less likely to adopt advanced accounting techniques. This issue is particularly evident in smaller cities, where the necessary infrastructure for providing MA services is lacking. Under such conditions, RE often rely on traditional methods, which can reduce the efficiency and quality of the services offered.

The findings of this study underscore the influence of environmental and legal factors on the performance of MA, aligning with the research by Gunarathne et al. (2021). That study highlights the role of environmental impacts and regulatory requirements in the development of MA, emphasizing how external pressures and government oversight shape the use of AS. Similarly, the present study identifies regulatory instability and insufficient oversight as major obstacles to enhancing the performance of MA services in Iran. On the other hand, Vu et al. (2022) identify changes in organizational structures and market pressures as key drivers in the implementation of MA services. These findings are consistent with the current research, emphasizing the need for effective strategies to address economic pressures. However, discrepancies arise between the current study and some prior research regarding access to advanced technologies and skilled human resources. While previous studies have highlighted significant challenges in adopting modern accounting techniques, this research clearly points out that a lack of training and

insufficient investment in human and technological resources hinder the effective implementation of advanced accounting methods. This difference may be attributable to recent changes in the labor market and new investments in education and technology, which earlier studies might not have addressed. Ultimately, the findings of this research stress the necessity of establishing structured frameworks and efficient strategies to tackle the challenges in the MA services market. Focusing on improving regulations, creating robust regulatory bodies, and investing in modern technologies could enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of this sector. Additionally, prioritizing education and the development of skilled human resources in this field is essential. These factors not only contribute to improving the quality of MA services but also foster greater trust among clients and stakeholders. As business complexities and competitive markets increase, the need for accurate cost allocation and better decision-making will be considered a competitive advantage. Additionally, the rapid growth of information technology and advancements in technology cannot be understood and executed by traditional individuals, and people must develop in line with their environment. On the other hand, strategic decisions require strategic information, which can only be achieved through continuous education and the use of technology.

Limitations and future researches

Limitations are an inherent part of any research. Regarding the limitations of this study, it is important to note that, given the general lack of use of MA systems among RE, the insufficient knowledge of respondents may limit the generalizability of the findings to RE outside the studied geographical scope.

For future research, it is recommended to explore the social and cultural influences on the adoption of MA services, as cultural attitudes and beliefs may play a significant role in their utilization. Additionally, conducting comparative studies of the MA services market across different countries could help identify best practices and effective strategies. The importance of this lies in the economic, cultural, legal, and regulatory differences, as well as the nature of the market (whether free or monopolistic), all of which significantly influence the strategies and practices in the Management Accounting services market. Research on the application of modern technologies, such as artificial intelligence and advanced software, could also have a significant impact on improving the performance of MA. Furthermore, examining the specific challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in adopting MA services could provide valuable insights into the unique needs and issues of these entities.

Assessing the impact of global economic changes on the development trends of the MA services market is also a crucial topic for future research. Lastly, exploring the application of fuzzy logic in optimizing accounting processes could contribute significantly to enhancing financial and managerial decision-making.

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